

HAYDOVCHILARNING PSIXOLOGIK SALOMATLIGI VA UNING MEZONLARI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada haydovchilarning psixologik salomatligi va uning mezonlari haqida turli fikrlar keltirib o'tilgan hamda tahlil qilingan. Maqola davomida asosli fikr hamda mulohazalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: haydovchilarning psixologik salomatligi, diqqatni rivojlantirish, transport vositasini haydash.

PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF DRIVERS AND ITS CRITERIA

Abstract. This article presents and analyzes various opinions about the psychological health of drivers and its criteria. Reasonable opinions and comments are given throughout the article.

Key words: psychological health of drivers, development of attention, driving a vehicle.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ЗДОРОВЬЕ ВОДИТЕЛЕЙ И ЕГО КРИТЕРИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены и проанализированы различные мнения о психологическом здоровье водителей и его критериях. Обоснованные мнения и комментарии даны на протяжении всей статьи.

Ключевые слова: психологическое здоровье водителей, развитие внимания, управление транспортным средством.

Dunyo aholisining ko'pchiligi uchun transport vositasini haydash odamlar turli maqsadlarda - ish joyiga, o'qishga, uyiga, yozgi uyiga yoki do'koniga borish uchun bajaradigan oddiy kundalik ishdir. Ammo ularning ba'zilar uchun bu harakatlar majmui ma'lum qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi va salbiy his-tuyg'ularni, ba'zan hatto qo'rquv va o'z mashinasiga o'tirishni istamaslik hissini keltirib chiqaradi. Ushbu muammodan aziyat chekayotganlarning ko'pchiligi uni hech qanday aniq hodisa bilan, masalan, yo'l-transport hodisasi bilan bog'lamaydi; aksincha, transport vositasini boshqarish qo'rquvi ko'pchilik odamlarda to'satdan, oldingi salbiy daqiqalarsiz namoyon bo'ladi. Xo'sh, bunday haydovchilarga ular uchun kundalik muammolarga sabab bo'lgan psixologik hodisani engib o'tishga va yana o'z avtomobillari bilan "do'stlashishga" qanday yordam berishimiz mumkin? Jismoniy faollik Jismoniy faollik va sport mashqlari haydovchiga sayohat oldidan hissiy stress va charchoqni yo'qotish imkonini beradi. Ushbu maslahat og'ir kundan keyin tunda haydashda eng samarali hisoblanadi. Bunday holatda, siz darhol g'ildirak orqasiga o'tmasligingiz kerak, ba'zi baquvvat harakatlar qilish, pulsni va nafas olish chuqurligini oshirish kerak. Ertalab ertalab haydash bo'lsa, oldingi jismoniy faollik tananing uyg'onishiga va transport vositasini boshqarish uchun zarur bo'lgan energiyani olishiga imkon beradi. Avtomobilni boshqarish bilan bog'liq harakatlarga maksimal e'tiborni jamlash harakatning har qanday ishtirokchisiga og'ir tirbandlikda o'zini ishonchli his qilish imkonini beradi. Yo'l harakati holatini kuzatishga xalaqit beradigan qo'shimcha tirnash xususiyati beruvchi moddalar sonini kamaytirish kerak: telefon suhbatlari, musiqa diskklarini almashtirish, radiostansiyalarni qidirish, chekish, haydash paytida ovqatlanish. SAO haydovchilik maktablariga ko'ra, qo'shimcha tashqi ogohlantirishlar haydash sifatini va yo'l-transport hodisasi xavfini yomonlashtirishi mumkin. Haydovchilarning psixologik muammolari Haydovchi o'rindig'i va orqa ko'zgu oynalarini to'g'ri sozlash Haydovchi o'rindig'ining ergonomik holati haydash paytida ortiqcha charchoq hissini

yo'qotadi, diqqatni turli yo'l ob'ektlariga qaratish vaqtini oshiradi, shuningdek, haydashda ishonchni oshiradi. Mohirlik bilan sozlangan orqa ko'rinish nometallari "o'lik zonalar" deb ataladigan magistralda harakatlanayotganda yomon ko'rinadigan joylar sonini kamaytiradi. Haydovchilarning psixologik muammolari Marshrutingiz bilan tanishing O'z avtomobilini haydashdan qo'rqqan haydovchilar uchun Suv stadionidagi haydovchilik maktabi haydash paytida salbiy ta'sirlarni va chalg'itishni kamaytirish uchun kelajakdagi sayohatingiz yo'nalishini oldindan o'rganishni tavsiya qiladi. Yo'l belgilarini, svetoforlarni o'rnatish joylarini, yo'l belgilarini va harakat yo'nalishlarini o'zgartirishni aniqlash kerak. Yangi marshrutni mustaqil ravishda o'rganish uchun eng yaxshi vaqt erta tong yoki dam olish kunlari tirbandlik eng past bo'lgan va sharoitlar eng qulaydir. Chuqur va xotirjam nafas olib, biz miyaga maksimal kislorod miqdorini etkazib beramiz. Shu bilan birga, haydovchi uchun eng muhim tizimlar va organlarning ishlashi yaxshilanadi. Shunday qilib, diqqatni jamlash, ko'rish keskinligi va harakatni muvofiqlashtirish uchun mas'ul bo'lgan tizimlar aniqroq va silliq ishlay boshlaydi. Haydovchilarning psixologik muammolari Boshqacha qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, psixolog va shifokorlar yordamisiz o'z kuchingiz bilan mashina haydash qo'rquvini engishingiz mumkin. Bu, birinchi navbatda, salbiy his-tuyg'ularning sababini, ularning namoyon bo'lish tabiati va chastotasini aniqlash, keyin esa mutaxassislarining yuqoridagi tavsiyalariga amal qilish kerak. Yangi haydovchilar uchun maslahatlar Shoshilish kerak emas Ajam haydovchi uchun haydashning barcha elementlarini tez va aniq bajarish juda qiyin bo'lishi tabiiy, bu ko'pincha boshqa yo'l foydalanuvchilarining noroziligiga sabab bo'ladi. Bunday vaziyatda sizga har tomondan signal berilganda, hamma asabiylashadi, lekin siz taslim bo'lolmaysiz. Siz mavhum bo'lishingiz, o'zingizni tashqi ogohlantirishlardan ajratib olishingiz va hech qanday holatda vahima qo'ymasligingiz kerak. Shuni aniq tushunish kerakki, asabiylashish yoki asabiylashish holatida haydovchining e'tibori sezilarli darajada zaiflashadi, bu oxir-oqibat jiddiy muammolarga olib kelishi mumkin. Shunday qilib, agar boshqa yo'l foydalanuvchilari sizga sekin yoki noto'g'ri ish qilayotganingizni ko'rsatsa, avval mashina atrofidagi vaziyatni xotirjam baholang va manevrni juda shoshilmasdan bajaring. Misol uchun, agar sizni kuzatib borayotgan maxsus xizmatlar, politsiya yoki tez yordam mashinasi haydovchisi zudlik bilan yo'l berishni talab qilsa, siz darhol "qochib ketishingiz" shart emas - vaziyatni xotirjam baholang va qayta tiklang. Haydovchilarning psixologik muammolari Yaxshi kayfiyat va kuchli his-tuyg'ular yo'q Kuchli hissiy tajribalar holatida mashinani boshqarish, ham salbiy, ham kuchli ijobiy, tajribali haydovchilar, hatto yangi boshlanuvchilar uchun ham tavsiya etilmaydi. Bunday holatda haydash charchoqlari odatdagidan tezroq boshlanadi, diqqat tarqaladi va bu muqarrar ravishda xatolarga olib keladi, ba'zan juda qo'pol va bezovta qiladi. Noaniq haydab yurgan yangi boshlanuvchilar uchun bu fakt hal qiluvchi rol o'ynashi mumkin. Shunday qilib, faqat yaxshi kayfiyatda rulga o'ting va yo'l davomida yo'l harakati holatiga to'liq e'tiboringizni qaratishga harakat qiling va bu faqat xotirjamlik va muvozanat holatida mumkin. Afsuski, bu haqiqat! Biz hammamiz insonmiz va odamlar xato qiladi va bu yaxshi. Zamonaviy dunyoda katta metropolda mashina haydash va xato qilmaslik deyarli mumkin emas, ba'zan hatto juda jiddiy. Odatiy misol - siz hatto borligini bilmagan yo'l belgilarini to'sib qo'yadigan to'xtab turgan katta transport vositasi. Yana bir misol, reklamaning ko'pligida, hatto tajribali haydovchilar uchun ham yo'l belgilarini sezish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin, ayniqsa belgilar o'ng tomonda joylashgan bo'lsa va hatto qisman daraxt shoxlari bilan to'sqinlik qilsa va siz keng yo'l bo'ylab harakatlanayotgan bo'lsangiz. chap bo'lakda. Bularning barchasini yodda tutishimiz va muayyan vaziyatda boshqa

yo'l harakati qatnashchilarining harakatlarini oldindan aytib berishga va profilaktika choralari ko'rishga harakat qilishimiz kerak. Va bu avtomatik ravishda boshqa avtoullovchilar duch keladigan qiyinchiliklarga befarq qolmasligini anglatadi. Misol uchun, agar siz boshqa haydovchi xatoga yo'l qo'yganini va u shunchaki boradigan joyi yo'q holatda bo'lganini ko'rsangiz va haqiqiy baxtsiz hodisa xavfi mavjud bo'lsa, dono bo'ling va xavfni bartaraf etish uchun barcha choralarni ko'ring (masalan, boshqa transport vositasi o'tishi uchun sekinlashtiring yoki boshqa transport vositasini manevr qilish uchun joy ochish uchun keyingi qatorga o'ting). Haydovchilarning psixologik muammolari Haydovchilarning psixologik muammolari Siz raqobatda emassiz va sizning atrofingizda raqiblar yo'q Ba'zi avtoullovchilar "mening yo'lim, men beparvo haydovchini o'tkazib yubormayman" tamoyiliga ko'ra haydashadi, ular boshqa transport vositasini qayta qurish paytida ataylab tezlashadilar va hatto har tomonlama signal berishadi. Ehtimol, bunday haydovchilar boshqa haydovchilarning xatti-harakatlarini shaxsiy haqorat sifatida qabul qilishlari mumkin, hech bo'lmaganda tashqaridan shunday ko'rinadi. Psixologik nuqtai nazardan, yo'lda bunday xatti-harakatlar qabul qilinishi mumkin emas, chunki bu muqarrar ravishda his-tuyg'ularning kuchayishiga (tajovuzkorlik, tirnash xususiyati) va natijada tez charchash va e'tiborni yo'qotishga olib keladi. Oxir-oqibat, bu shunchaki xavfsiz emas, chunki to'qnashuv haydovchilarni tushunmaslik, tajribasizlik va eng og'ir holatlarda "prinsiplik" tufayli sodir bo'lishi mumkin. Shunday qilib, boshqa yo'l foydalanuvchilarini raqib sifatida qabul qilmang, siz raqobatda emassiz! Sizning maqsadingiz "A" nuqtasidan "B" nuqtasiga xavfsiz o'tishdir. Agar kimdir sizning oldingizda qayta qurishni boshlagan bo'lsa, uni o'tkazib yuboring, hech qanday holatda aralashmang. Hech kimni qasddan to'sib qo'yishga urinmang, atrofingizdagilarning hammasiga kerakli joyga borishlariga imkon bering – bu xavfsiz haydashning asosiy tamoyillaridan biridir. Har bir haydovchi o'z "dasturi" bo'yicha haydaydi va sizdan tezroq va tezroq haydaydiganlarga havas qilib bo'lmaydi. Va shunga qaramay, tezligi siz uchun eng qulay bo'lgan qatorni tanlashga harakat qiling. Shuni aniq tushunish kerakki, agar siz chap bo'lakda oqim tezligidan past tezlikda harakat qilsangiz va shu bilan uni sekinlashtirsangiz, bu boshqa haydovchilar tomonidan hurmatsizlik harakati sifatida qabul qilinishi va hatto tajovuzga olib kelishi mumkin (kesish, quvib o'tish va to'satdan tormozlash va hokazo.). Xulosa Haydovchi xulq-atvorining to'g'ri psixologik munosabatini tanlash yo'l harakati xavfsizligini ta'minlashning asosiy tarkibiy qismlaridan biridir. Xavfsiz haydash uchun faqat tinch va muvozanatli holatda haydash va haydash paytida e'tiboringizni imkon qadar yo'l harakati holatiga qarating. Sizni shoshayotgan boshqa haydovchilarning provokatsiyalariga berilmang, haydashning barcha elementlarini shoshilmasdan, xotirjam bajaring. Boshqa yo'l foydalanuvchilariga e'tiborli bo'ling, hurmat ko'rsating, shunda sizga ham xuddi shunday munosabatda bo'ladi. Shunday qilib, xorijlik ham, mahalliy tadqiqotchilar ham XX asrgacha psixik holatlarni alohida toifaga ajratmaganlar. Shu bilan birga, ruhiy holatlarning mohiyatini tushunish yo'lida muhim qadamlar qo'yildi: holat va uni boshdan kechirayotgan shaxs o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikning ajralmasligi haqida, ruhiy holatlar va ruhiy jarayonlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik haqida, diqqat - bu holat, ruhiy holat, ruhiy holat. holat - bu ma'lum vaqt davomida turli xil ruhiy jarayonlarni qamrab oladigan murakkab ruhiy shakllanish. Ruhiy holatlar, ruhiy hayotning boshqa hodisalari kabi, ko'pincha tashqi muhit ta'siridan iborat bo'lgan o'z sabablariga ega. Kundalik va kasbiy hayotda ko'pchilik odamlarga xos bo'lgan eng keng tarqalgan va tipik ruhiy holatlar quyidagi holatlardir: Optimal ish sharoiti - o'rtacha sur'at va intensivlikda amalga oshiriladigan faoliyatning maksimal samaradorligini ta'minlaydi

(kontsentratsiyani oshirish, faol fikrlash, xotirani keskinlashtirish va maqsadning mavjudligi) Kuchli mehnat faoliyati holati - ekstremal sharoitlarda ish paytida (ruhiy stress, asab tizimining faolligi oshishi) Kasbiy qiziqish holati - mehnat unumdorligida muhim rol o'ynaydi (kasbiy faoliyatning amalga oshirilgan ahamiyati, bajarilgan ish haqida iloji boricha ko'proq ma'lumot olish istagi va istagi) Shuningdek, monotonlik, charchoq, stress va boshqalar. Ruhiy holatlar tuzilishini o'rganish holatlarning shakllanishining beshta faktini aniqlashga imkon berdi: kayfiyat, muvaffaqiyat ehtimolini baholash, motivatsiya darajasi, uyg'onish darajasi (tonik komponent) va faoliyatga munosabat. Ushbu besh fakt o'z vazifalari bo'yicha har xil bo'lgan uchta davlat guruhiga birlashtirilgan: 1) Motivatsion - rag'batlantirish (kayfiyat va motivatsiya) 2) Hissiy - baholovchi 3) Faollashtirish - energiya (uyg'onish darajasi). Eng muhim va mazmunli motivatsion - rag'batlantiruvchi davlatlar guruhidir. Ularning funktsiyalariga uning faoliyati sub'ekti tomonidan ongli ravishda rag'batlantirish, uni amalga oshirish uchun ixtiyoriy harakatlarni kiritish kiradi. Bu holatlarga quyidagilar kiradi: qiziqish, mas'uliyat, konsentratsiya va boshqalar. Ikkinchi guruh holatlari funktsiyasi - bu ehtiyojlarning hissiy tajribasi, ushbu faoliyatga munosabatni baholash va unga asoslangan faoliyat uchun motivatsiya shakllanishining boshlang'ich, ongsiz bosqichidir. uning tugallanishi - natijani baholash, shuningdek, faoliyatning mumkin bo'lgan muvaffaqiyati yoki muvaffaqiyatsizligini prognoz qilish. Uchinchi guruh holatlarining boshqa barcha holatlardan oldingi vazifasi uyg'onish - psixikaning ham, butun organizmning ham faolligini yo'q qilishdir. Faoliyatning uyg'onishi qondirishni talab qiladigan ehtiyojning paydo bo'lishi, faoliyatning yo'qolishi - ehtiyojdan zavqlanish yoki charchoq bilan bog'liq.

REFERENCES

1. Mohinur, D., & Rahimjon, U. (2022). A Study Of Memory Processes And Their Development In Preschool. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 62-65.
2. Rahim, U. (2021, May). SOCIAL FACTORS OF THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 6-7).
3. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLAR XULQIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK G'AYRATLILIK XUSUSIYATLARI TADQIQ ETISH METODOLOGIYASI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 127-135.
4. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRI SHAXSIGA XOS ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDOSHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 120-126.
5. Raxmonovich U. R. O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI //INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 87-97.
6. Raxmonovich, Usmonov Rahimjon. "O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI." *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION* 1.12 (2022): 87-97.
7. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON

- BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
8. Raxmonovich U. R. O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI // *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 87-97.
 9. Raxmonovich, Usmonov Rahimjon. "O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI." *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION* 1.12 (2022): 87-97.
 10. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
 11. Rakhmonovich U. R. CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE // *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 12. – C. 820-824.
 12. Rakhmonovich, Usmanov Rahimjon. "CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 820-824.
 13. Rakhmonovich, U. R. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 820-824.
 14. Rakhmanovich R. U., Rakhmanovna U. F. EASTERN THINKERS'VIEWS ON NATIONAL FOLK GAMES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY // *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 3.
 15. Rakhmanovich, Rahim Usmanov, and Usmanova Feruza Rakhmanovna. "EASTERN THINKERS'VIEWS ON NATIONAL FOLK GAMES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.3 (2023).
 16. Rakhmanovich, R. U., & Rakhmanovna, U. F. (2023). EASTERN THINKERS'VIEWS ON NATIONAL FOLK GAMES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
 17. Rakhmanovich R. U., Rakhmanovna U. F. EASTERN THINKERS'VIEWS ON NATIONAL FOLK GAMES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY // *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 3.
 18. Rakhmanovich, Rahim Usmanov, and Usmanova Feruza Rakhmanovna. "EASTERN THINKERS'VIEWS ON NATIONAL FOLK GAMES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON

- THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.3 (2023).
19. Rakhmanovich, R. U., & Rakhmanovna, U. F. (2023). EASTERN THINKERS' VIEWS ON NATIONAL FOLK GAMES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
 20. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
 21. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O 'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 176-182.
 22. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILIIY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
 23. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGUISTICS AND THE HISTORY OF ITS ANALYTICAL DEVELOPMENT. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 99-105.
 24. Vosiljonov, A., & Isaqova, X. (2023). EFFECTIVENESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION IN THE PRIMARY GRADES. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(2).
 25. Нажмиддинов, Э., & Мухамедиев, М. (2023). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
 26. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., & Мухаммадиев, М. А. (2022). ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИНИНГ ТУР ТАРКИБИ. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 60-68.
 27. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х. (2022). ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИ. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 189-194.
 28. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF NATURE IN THE FORMATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE IDEAL GENERATION. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 149-154.
 29. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). " ICHTHYOLOGY AND HYDROBIOLOGY" PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIRECTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 152-160.
 30. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE NEED TO IMPROVE HUMAN'S NOOSPHERICAL RELATIONSHIP TO NATURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(11), 23-30.
 31. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM IN IMPROVING PERSONAL ECOLOGICAL CULTURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(11), 5-12.

32. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). АТРОФ-МУҲИТНИ АСРАШ БЎЙИЧА МИЛЛИЙ СТРАТЕГИК РЕЖА ВА УНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(2), 251-258.
33. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). ЯНГИ ТАРАҚҚИЁТ БОСҚИЧИДА ЭКОЛОГИК МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯЛАШ ДАСТУРИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 1179-1186.
34. Абдумаликов, А. А. (2019). Human and Natural Harmony in the Historical Process. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 205-209.
35. Abidzhanovich, A. A. (2020). Issues Of Formation Of Rationality In Relations Of Nature With Society. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(08), 301-304.
36. Abdumalikov, A. A. (2019). Environmental Ecological Policy in Uzbekistan and Necessity Of Formation Of Rational Communication To Nature. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(9), 94-101.
37. Мирзобоев, Й. А. (2022). Тур Ўзгариш Чизиқлари Учта Бўлган, Гиперболик Қисмларининг Ҳаммаси Характеристик Учбурчаклардан Иборат Бўлган Бешбурчакли Соҳада Учинчи Тартибли Кўринишдаги Параболик-Гиперболик Тенглама Учун Битта Чегаравий Масала Ҳақида. *Theory And Analytical Aspects Of Recent Research*, 1(5), 363-366.
38. MIRZABOYEV, Y. BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QITUVCHILARINING MATEMATIKA O 'QITISH METODIKASI. O 'RTA UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA MATEMATIKA O 'QITISHNING MAQSADI. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 169-172.
39. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
40. Курбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
41. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
42. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). O 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
43. Iminov, B. B. (2020). INNOVATIVE CULTURAL LINKS ARE AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(3), 263-270.
44. Iminov, B. B. (2019). A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO INNOVATIVA AND CULTURAL-RELATIONS AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(5), 157-162.
45. Dilfuza, S., Nabijonova, F., & Matlubaxon, A. (2022). TA'LIM VA O'QITISH NAZARIYASINING MUHIM JIHLTLARI. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 2(19), 366-372.

46. Nabijonova, F. (2022). Boshlangich sinflarda didaktik oyinlarning ahamiyati: Nabijonova Feruza. *Qo'qon universitetining ilmiy materiallar bazasi*, 1(000006).
47. Nabijonova, F. (2022). BOSHLANGICH SINFLARDA OZGA GAPNING QOLLANILISHI. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 2(19), 180-184.
48. НАБИЖОНОВА, Ф. ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ. *ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ Учредители: ООО "Институт управления и социально-экономического развития"*, (10), 90-92.
49. Набижонова, Ф. (2022). ОНА ТИЛИ ВА АДАБИЁТ ТАЪЛИМИНИНГ ТАРИХИ ВА ТАРАҚҚИЁТ ЙЎЛЛАРИ. *Мировая наука*, (10 (67)), 38-41.
50. Feruza, N. (2023). Characteristics of the Lessons of the Native Language. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(3), 32-36.
51. Kosimova, X. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF READING CULTURE IN THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY SPIRITUAL CLIMATE IN THE FAMILY. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(10), 7-13.
52. Qosimova, X. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LIBRARY CULTURE IN FORMING A HEALTHY SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE FAMILY. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 142-148.
53. Qosimova, X. (2022). OILADA SOG'LOM MA'NAVIY MUHITNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA KITOBXONLIK MADANIYATINING AHAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 142-148.
54. ҚОСИМОВА, Х., & КАРИМОВА, Г. ЭКОНОМИКА И СОЦИУМ. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 612-615.
55. Джалолова, М. (2021). Эъзоза Юлдашевна Рахманова, and Холида Набиевна Косимова.". *ВОСПИТАНИЕ СЕНСОРНОГО ВОСПРИЯТИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА." Scientific progress*, 1.
56. Buzrukova, D. M. (2023). “МУНАВВАТ” HISSIY KONSEPTINING TURLI LINGVOMADANIYAT VAKILLARI IDROKIDAGI TASVIRI. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(1), 178-183.
57. Бузрукова, Д. (2022). ҲИС-ТУЙҒУЛАР УНИВЕРСАЛЛИГИ ВА ҲИССИЙ-ЛИСОНИЙ ОЛАМ МАНЗАРАСИГА ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИК ЁНДАШУВ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(11), 239-242.
58. Mamurkhanovna, D. B. (2022). The Concept Of “Love” As An Important Element Of The Emotional World Landscape. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(5), 95-98.
59. Tursunova, D. T., Abobakirova, O. N., Buzrukova, D. M., Mahmudova, O. T., Ubaydullayeva, Z. H., & Kholmatova, N. N. (2022). Principal Principles And Important Factors Of Student Women's Social Activity. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6262-6269.
60. Buzrukova, D. M. M. (2023). TARBIYACHI VA OTA-ONALARNING O 'ZARO HURMATGA ASOSLANGAN MULOQOTINING KALIT FAKTORLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4), 793-797.

61. Buzrukova, D. M. (2023). Muhabbat" konseptining lingvomadaniy o'ziga xosligi. *FarDU. ILMIY XABARLAR*, 1, 318-321.
62. Abdugufurovna, J. N., & Turgunovna, M. S. (2022). The Problems In Teaching Language. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 16(5), 46-48.
63. Jumaniyazova, N. A. O., & Mavlonova, S. T. U. (2022). CHET TILINI O'RGATISHDA KOMMUNIKATIV PRINSIPLAR HAMDA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYANING ROLI. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(2), 118-122.
64. Turg'Unovna, M. S. (2022). Yangi O'zbekistonda diniy-dunyoviy qarashlar. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 8, 115-120.
65. Ernazarov, G., & Mavlonova, S. (2023). INDICATORS OF SPEED PHYSICAL QUALITY OF STUDENTS. *Science and innovation*, 2(B1), 177-183.
66. Boboyeva, Z. A., & Mo'Minova, D. B. Q. (2022). TALABALARNING KREATIVLIK QOBILIYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 221-233.
67. Zulfiya, B., & Raxmonali, S. (2022). SAN'ATNING IJTIMOY HAYOTNING MURAKKAB MUNOSABATLARI BILAN ALOQADORLIGI. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 296-300.
68. Бобоева, З. (2022). ИЖТИМОЙ ФАОЛЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ТАСВИРИЙ САЊАТНИНГ ЎРНИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 51-55.
69. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 256-259.
70. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 215-221.
71. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH-IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 66-70.
72. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o'g'li, V. A. (2022). XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 39-47.
73. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Sportchi Psixologik Salomatligiga Ta'sir Etuvchi Omillar. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 117-121.
74. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2023). SPEECH ISSUES IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. *IQRO JURNALI*, 2(2), 503-511.
75. Abduraxmonov, A., & Kadirov, S. (2022). DEMOGRAFIK JARAYONLARNING IQTISODIY-IJTIMOY SOHALARNI RIVOJLANISHI BILAN BOG 'LIQLIGI VA DASTLABKI XUSUSIY MULK MASALALARI. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 222-229.

76. Siddikov, F. Z. (2023). BASKETBOLCHI BOLALAR VA O'SMIRLARNING JISMONIY RIVOJLANISHINING XUSUSIYATLARI. *Ustozlar uchun*, 43(3), 120-123.
77. Сиддигов, Ф., & Эшимов, Т. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВЛЕННОСТИ ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА НА ОСНОВЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ДВИГАТЕЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 2(23), 41-44.
78. Farrux, S. (2022). SPORT O 'YINLARINING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI, 1(2), 184-189.
79. Sayidolimov, J. B. O. G. L. (2023). AGIOGRAFIK OBRAZLARNING MAZMUN-MOHİYATIDAGI EVRILISHLAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(3), 1318-1322.
80. Odiljon o'g'li, U. D. (2023). ADABIY ASAR QAHRAMONI TALQINIDAGI O 'ZIGA XOSLIKLAR. *IQRO JURNALI*, 2(2), 777-785.
81. Kholmatova, Z. T., & Kholikova, D. M. (2022). MODEL OF DEVELOPING AND DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENTS. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 190-195.
82. Dilobarkhon, K. (2019). The importance of modern innovation in education. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
83. Kholikova, D. (2020). INTELLECTUAL ACTIVITY OF CREATIVE THINKING VERBAL TEST "UNUSUAL USE". *PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES*, 22.
84. Maxsitovna, K. D. (2022). Pedagogical Problems of Child Raising in the Uzbek Family. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 542-546.
85. Xolmatova, Z. T., & Xolikova, D. M. (2022). TALABALARDA INNOVASION FIKRLASH KO'NIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MODELI. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 139-144.
86. Холикова, Д. (2021). Возможности диагностики эффективности компенсационного подхода в обучении. *Общество и инновации*, 2(9/S), 239-252.
87. Kholikova, D. M. (2021). THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF INCREASING INNOVATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 422-424.
88. Kholikova, D. M. (2021). DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 549-552.
89. Kholmatova, Z. T. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF GENDER ASPECTS OF EDUCATION. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(10), 60-65.
90. Kholmatova, Z. T., & Kholikova, D. M. (2022). MODEL OF DEVELOPING AND DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENTS. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 190-195.
91. Xolmatova, Z. T., & Xolikova, D. M. (2022). TALABALARDA INNOVASION FIKRLASH KO'NIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MODELI. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 139-144.

92. Kholmatova, Z., & Axmadaliyeva, M. (2022). Healthy lifestyle (HLS)-The basis of valeology in kindergarten. *Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research*, 11(9), 136-139.
93. Kholmatova, Z., & Olamnazarova, F. (2022). Problems of the communicational approach of language teaching in the primary class. *Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research*, 11(9), 140-144.
94. Tillavoldievna, K. Z. (2022). Problems of Family Education in People's Pedagogy. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 535-541.
95. Холматова, З. Т. (2022). ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА ГЕНДЕРЛИИ ЁНДАШУВ ДАВР ТАЛАБИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(3), 134-140.
96. Tillavoldievna, K. Z. (2022). Problems of Family Education in People's Pedagogy. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 535-541.
97. То'лқиновна, Y. D. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA МАТЕМАТИК TASAVVURLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
98. Yuldasheva Dilshoda То'лқиновна (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
99. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.
100. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
101. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 914-917.
102. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 1040-1044.
103. Alimjanova, M. (2021). About Gender Stereotypes. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning*, 2(6), 1-5.
104. Yunusovna, A. M. (2021). Pedagogical system of responsibility formation in primary school students based on national staff. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(06), 1-7.
105. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK МАКТАВ YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
106. Курбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
107. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).

108. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). O 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
109. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 914-917.
110. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 1040-1044.
111. Alimjanova, M. (2021). About Gender Stereotypes. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning*, 2(6), 1-5.
112. Yunusovna, A. M. (2021). Pedagogical system of responsibility formation in primary school students based on national staff. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(06), 1-7.
113. To'liqinova, Y. D. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MATEMATIK TASAVVURLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
114. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To'liqinova (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
115. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.
116. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
117. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Developing Critical Thinking In Primary School Students. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
118. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
119. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.
120. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.
121. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 235-239.
122. Maxamadaliyevna, Y. D., Oljayevna, O. F., Qizi, T. D. T., Shavkatovna, S. R. N., & Anvarovna, A. O. (2020). Pedagogical Features Of Mental Development Of Preschool Children. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6), 14221-14225.

123. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2022). THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 10, 128-133.
124. Шарофутдинова, Р. Ш. (2022). БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИДА ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МОДЕЛИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(3), 149-158.
125. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AS A SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL NECESSITY. *Open Access Repository*, 4(03), 51-59.
126. Aminova, F., Ahlimirzayev, A., & Sharofiddinova, R. (2023). USING THE PRINCIPLE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RELATIONSHIP IN STUDYING DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS IN SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS AND ACADEMIC LYCEUMS.
127. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 424-429.
128. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). THE ACTUAL STATUS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(12), 206-213.
129. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINING AMALIYOTDA QOLLASH. *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(7), 54-58.